

model (13-14) and over a wide range for DNA model from pH 4 to 10.

Fig. 2 pH-rate profile for the pH-independent hydrolysis of (■) is for (UpU) at 90°C and (●) is 4-NPNp*P (2) at 100 °C over a range of pH (measured at 100°C). (○) is HPNPP (1) at 37°C

Fig. 3 Relationship between different temperatures (100 – 160°C) and rate constants (s^{-1}) (■) represents pH-independent hydrolysis of HPNPP (1) in 0.03 M acetate buffer (pH 4.7) and (●) is spontaneous hydrolysis of (4-NPNp*P) 2 in 0.05 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 6.5)

Fig. 3 shows an Eyring plot of good results obtained in 0.05 M potassium phosphate buffer pH 6.5 for **2** and 0.03 M potassium acetate buffer pH 4.7. Extrapolating of obtained results indicates that, at 25°C, the apparent first-order rate constant is $k_{25} = 1 \times 10^{-10} s^{-1}$ for hydrolysis of **1** and **2**. An Eyring plot based on data points gathered over the lowest reactivity of pH according to pH-rate profiles of **1** and **2**, indicates that ΔH^\ddagger 62.2 $kJ mol^{-1}$ for DNA model reaction, and ΔS^\ddagger -165 $J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$, but RNA model gives ΔH^\ddagger 108.9 $kJ mol^{-1}$ and ΔS^\ddagger -65.9 $J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$. The activation parameters for the hydrolysis of 4-NPNp*P (**2**) is very similar to that for Me-2,4-DNPP- and bis-2,4-DNPP- in H_2O , ΔH^\ddagger 59.5 and 79.5 $kJ mol^{-1}$, ΔS^\ddagger -131 and -107 $J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$ [15]-[16].

The similarity between the extrapolated rates of DNA and RNA models at 25°C, implies that under neutral conditions

seems the hydroxyl group at position C-2' does not play a clear role in the mechanism. Thus, it seems reasonable to draw a mechanism as shown below, where the substrate acting as a general base is a more likely mechanism than the direct attack of H_2O as a nucleophile.

Fig. 4 Suggested mechanism for the cleavage of RNA and DNA models (**1** and **2**) in pH-independent reactions.

Measurements of the hydrolysis of **1** and **2** as simple alkyl-aryl phosphate diesters have been used to provide a better estimate of the stability of DNA and RNA towards hydrolytic P-O cleavage, ($k_{25} = 1 \times 10^{-10} s^{-1}$ at 25°C for both).

III. CONCLUSION

The kinetic results presented here provide strong evidence of the similar mechanism for the cleavage of DNA and RNA under pH-independent conditions. Suggested mechanism can be drawn according similar extrapolated rates for activated models of DNA and RNA, which seems there is no an important role for the hydroxyl group at position C-2' (Ribonucleic acid RNA) as expected for that big role in basic reactions (Fig. 4).

IV. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2-hydroxy-1-propyl-4-nitrophenylphosphate diester **1** was prepared according to published procedure (17). 4-nitrophenyl-alkyl phosphate diester was successfully prepared by reacting 1 eq. of 2,2-dimethyl-3-phenyl propanol with a solution of 1 eq. of 4-nitrophenyl phosphoro-dichloridate with TEA in dry DCM while stirring at 3°C. The reaction mixture was left to reach room temperature and then stirred overnight under a nitrogen atmosphere. A solution of water with TEA was added into the reaction mixture to form the phosphate diester triethylammonium salt. Removal of the solvents yields the crude product with some by products. Consequently, the crude product was purified by silica gel chromatography and sulfonated to give 4-nitrophenyl-2,2-dimethyl-3-phenyl propanyl phosphate sodium salt **2**.

Kinetic experiments were carried out in the designed stainless steel vessels at 100 - 160 \pm 0.1°C in a circulating oil bath. Calculated amount of diester was dissolved in buffer solution containing 2.5 mg of benzoic acid as an internal reference. compound **1** (19.6 mg, 0.044 mmol) was dissolved in pre-heated solutions of phosphate or acetate buffers at needed temperature to yield a solution of 20 mM of the diester containing 4mM of the internal reference. The reaction mixture was loaded into the reaction vessels after tightening using a torque wrench and fully placed in a Grant circulating oil bath, the temperature of the bath was monitored and

maintained using a digital microprocessor thermometer. Aliquots from the reaction vessels (50 μ l) were taken at the desired time intervals after cooling. The sample was filtered by Chromacol 0.2 μ m syringe filter and analyzed by HPLC at λ_{\max} 224 nm, where all materials (substrate and products) can be monitored, benzoic acid selected as stable internal reference containing a similar chromophore at 224 nm. The 40 μ l was injected to completely fill the loading loop (20 μ l). This was loaded onto the column and eluted with solvent system of Acetonitrile and 0.1% TFA in H₂O at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. The pseudo-first-order rate constant was obtained by plotting the relative peak area against time.

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